

Research

Evaluation of Uncrushed Quartzite Gravel from Quaternary Alluvial Deposit of Central Nepal Sub-Himalaya for Railway Ballasts

Dinesh Raj Sharma¹, Naresh Kazi Tamrakar^{2*}

¹Central Department of Geology, Tribhuvan University, Kirtipur, Kathmandu, Nepal

²Central Department of Geology, Tribhuvan University, Kirtipur, Kathmandu, Nepal

Abstract: Railway ballast is essential for track stability, drainage, and load distribution in railway infrastructure. Traditionally, crushed stone has been the preferred ballast material due to its superior mechanical properties. However, growing demand for sustainable and cost-effective alternatives has prompted interest in natural aggregates such as uncrushed riverbed gravels. This study evaluates the suitability of uncrushed quartzite gravels, abundant in Central Nepal's Quaternary alluvial deposits, for railway ballast applications. A comprehensive series of laboratory tests assessed the physical, mechanical, and durability properties of the gravels, including specific gravity, water absorption, Los Angeles Abrasion (LAAB), Aggregate Impact Value (AIV), Aggregate Crushing Value (ACV), Point Load Strength Index (PLSI), Slake Durability Index (SDI), and Sulfate Soundness (SSV). The findings reveal that these gravels exhibit favorable properties, including low water absorption, high resistance to weathering and abrasion, and adequate mechanical strength to withstand heavy railway loads. These characteristics align with the requirements for durable and long-lasting ballast materials. Despite these advantages, some variability in strength and wear resistance was observed, as indicated by higher LAAB and ACV values in certain samples. This highlights the need for further investigation into the selection and processing of the gravels to ensure consistent performance. The results support the potential of uncrushed quartzite gravels as a sustainable alternative to traditional crushed stone ballast, offering environmental and economic benefits. However, factors such as source variability, mineralogical composition, and site-specific conditions must be considered. Optimizing the utilization of these gravels can contribute to the development of eco-friendly and cost-effective railway infrastructure in Nepal.

Keywords: Quartzite, Railway Ballasts, Strength, Durability, Sub-Himalaya

*Corresponding author's email: naresh.tamrakar@cdgl.tu.edu.np

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Introduction

Railway track ballast plays a vital role in ensuring operational safety, stability, and efficiency by distributing loads, enabling effective drainage, and maintaining lateral track stability (Selig & Sluz, 1978; Selig & Waters, 1994). While crushed stone is traditionally preferred for its superior mechanical and durability properties, naturally occurring uncrushed aggregates, such as riverbed gravels, have gained attention as sustainable and cost-effective alternatives

(Okonta & Magagula, 2011). In the Central Nepal Sub-Himalaya, uncrushed quartzite gravels derived from Quaternary alluvial deposits are abundant and exhibit significant engineering potential (Maharjan & Tamrakar, 2008; Pokharel & Tamrakar, 2022). The uncrushed quartzite gravels of this region, predominantly derived from quartzite rich conglomerates and quartzites, are a unique geological resource shaped by erosion and transportation processes, and are characterized by rounded to sub-rounded shapes, varying grain sizes, and surface textures (Maharjan & Tamrakar, 2008). Quartzite clasts dominate the composition, followed by sandstone and other rock types, with the proportion of quartzite increasing downstream due to the influence of source rocks in the Lesser Himalayan Range (Tamrakar & Shrestha, 2008; Pokharel & Tamrakar, 2022).

Uncrushed quartzite gravels exhibit inherent variability in mechanical and durability properties due to their natural formation processes. Wnek et al. (2013) highlight that the shape and angularity of aggregates significantly influence their strength and performance as railway ballast, with rounded aggregates generally showing lower strength due to reduced interlocking capabilities. Sharma & Tamrakar (2023) assess quartzites from Nepal, finding them to possess favorable physical and mechanical properties, including high slake durability and point load strength, making them suitable for railway applications. Maharjan & Tamrakar (2008) report that river gravels, primarily quartzite, demonstrate good workability and low water absorption, indicating their potential as construction aggregates. Okonta & Magagula (2011) emphasize that rounded ballasts are less affected by abrasion compared to angular ones, suggesting that while uncrushed quartzite gravels may have limitations, their geological significance and regional availability make them valuable for local infrastructure projects.

Several researches have evaluated crushed stones of various rock types, including granite, shale, and dolerite, for their suitability as ballast material (Indraratna et al., 1998; Okonta & Magagula, 2011; NÅlsund, 2014; Ngamkhanong et al., 2017). While sandstones from the Sub-Himalaya displayed poor resistance to abrasion (Budhathoki & Tamrakar, 2022), aggregates from the Trishuli Ganga River in the Lesser Himalayan stretch exhibited acceptable sulfate soundness and Los Angeles abrasion values, indicating their suitability for asphaltic and concrete uses (Shrestha & Tamrakar, 2013). Quartzite has been identified as a suitable material for railway ballast due to its favorable physical, mechanical and durability properties. Studies have shown that quartzite aggregates exhibit low water absorption, good soundness, and high resistance to crushing, impact, abrasion and chemical weathering (Maharjan & Tamrakar, 2008; Pokharel and Tamrakar, 2022; Sharma and Tamrakar, 2023). The angular shape and high density of quartzite particles contribute to effective interlocking and load-bearing capacity (Wnek et al., 2013). Quartzite ballasts typically demonstrate low water absorption, high slake durability, and good resistance to weathering (Sharma and Tamrakar, 2023). Comparative studies have revealed that concrete made from quartzite aggregates achieves higher compressive strength compared to other aggregate types (Abdullahi, 2012). However, the suitability of quartzite for ballast applications can vary depending on specific quarry sources and production techniques (Wnek et al., 2013). Overall, quartzite from appropriate sources generally meets or exceeds the established standards for railway ballast, making it a preferred choice for many railway projects.

Railway ballast properties are crucial for track performance and maintenance. Specific gravity and water absorption are crucial physical properties of materials, influencing their density, strength, and durability (Daku, 2017). Specific gravity is inversely proportional to water absorption (Ginting, 2022). Water absorption reflects a material's porosity and potential for water ingress (Preßler, 1924). These properties significantly affect mechanical behavior, with even small amounts of porosity impacting rock deformation under stress (Gratchev, 2019). Accurate measurement of these properties is essential for assessing material quality and suitability for various applications.

Key mechanical properties assessed include Los Angeles Abrasion Value (LAAB), Aggregate Impact Value (AIV), Aggregate Crushing Value (ACV), and Point Load Strength Index (PLSI) (NÅlsund, 2014; Pokharel and Tamrakar, 2022). These tests evaluate wear resistance, impact strength, compressive strength, and tensile strength, respectively. Flakiness index, roundness, and sphericity are additional properties considered (Okonta and Magagula, 2011). The Slake

Durability Index (SDI) is a standardized test that measures a rock's resistance to weakening and disintegration through repeated wetting and drying cycles, particularly useful for assessing clay-bearing rocks (Franklin and Chandra, 1972). The Sulfate Soundness Value (SSV), typically using magnesium sulfate, evaluates aggregate durability and resistance to weathering (Wu et al., 1998). Rock durability is influenced by various factors, including the original weathering state, imposed stresses during production and service, and environmental conditions (Fookes et al., 1988). The shape and size characteristics of railroad ballast significantly influence track stability and performance. Angular particles ensure good interlocking, enhancing lateral stability and shear resistance (Tutumluer et al., 2006; Xiao and Tutumluer, 2017). Particle size distribution plays a crucial role in drainage and load distribution, with uniform gradations recommended by AREMA (Boler et al., 2014). Proper selection of ballast materials is essential for reducing maintenance costs and ensuring long-term track stability (Pokharel and Tamrakar, 2022).

Railway ballast performance is influenced by mineralogical composition, texture and microstructures, which can be assessed through petrographic analysis (Watters et al., 1987). Quartzite is considered a suitable ballast material due to its favorable characteristics (Pokharel and Tamrakar, 2022). Key evaluation criteria for ballast include low abrasion, impact, and crushing values, high durability under weathering conditions, proper shape and size, and high specific gravity (Nålsund et al., 2013; Nålsund, 2014; Guo et al., 2022). Selection criteria and test methods for ballast quality quantification differ across countries, reflecting variations in local geologies and climatic conditions (Guo et al., 2022). Ongoing research explores alternative materials and technologies to enhance ballast performance and environmental sustainability.

Research on railway ballast materials highlights the importance of quartzite as a preferred option due to its high performance and reliability (Nålsund, 2014; Sharma and Tamrakar, 2023). However, studies have identified challenges with quartzite ballast, particularly its susceptibility to weathering in harsh environments. Research on railway ballast emphasizes the importance of quartzite's angular particles for enhanced interlocking and track stability (Wnek et al., 2013). Quartzite ballast demonstrates high resistance to fragmentation, indicated by a lower Los Angeles Abrasion Value (Nålsund, 2014). Its high specific gravity and low water absorption contribute to better performance under wet conditions (Shi et al., 2023). These properties ensure efficient load distribution and drainage, critical for maintaining track performance and reducing maintenance costs. However, natural abrasion over time can lead to more rounded particles and increased fouling, potentially affecting ballast strength and deformation properties (Rohrman et al., 2020). Hence, keeping in mind the usefulness of quartzite gravels as ballasts, this research focuses on two main objectives: (a) to analyze the physical, mechanical and durability characteristics of uncrushed natural gravels, and (b) to assess their suitability for railway ballasts by comparing the results against established standards

Geological Setting

The study area lies within the Sub-Himalayan Siwalik Group in central Nepal, comprising Quaternary alluvial deposits derived from the erosion and transport of materials from the Siwalik Hills (Figure 1). The Siwalik Group, extending east-west along the Himalayan range, is a Late Tertiary sedimentary formation divided into three main lithostratigraphic units: the Lower, Middle, and Upper Siwalik Subgroups (Hagen, 1969; Itihara et al., 1972; West and Munthe, 1981; Schelling, 1991). This sequence of continental molassic sediments was deposited in a southern foreland basin and subsequently uplifted by the Himalayan orogeny.

The Lower Siwalik Subgroup is characterized by fine to medium-grained sandstone, mudstone, and siltstone, deposited primarily in meandering river systems (Ulak, 2009; Syangbo and Tamrakar, 2013; Shrestha et al., 2019). Overlying this, the Middle Siwalik Subgroup consists of medium to coarse-grained sandstone with a distinctive "salt and pepper" texture, reflecting sediment transport and deposition in braided river systems (Adhikari and Sakai, 2015; Shrestha et al., 2019; Tamrakar and Karki, 2019). The Upper Siwalik Subgroup, dominating the southern parts of the region, comprises

pebble and cobble conglomerate beds interspersed with quartzite, schist, and granite clasts, deposited in high-energy fluvial systems (Tamrakar and Karki, 2019; Pradhananga and Tamrakar, 2016).

The Quaternary alluvial deposits in the Dun Valley, a prominent basin within the Sub-Himalayan region, form the focus of this study. These deposits primarily consist of cobble, pebble, and sand layers derived from rivers flowing from the Siwalik Hills. They are often poorly sorted with horizontally bedded clasts, indicating deposition in dynamic fluvial environments (Kimura, 1995; Sharma, 1990). The deposits in the Dun Valley are composed of quartzite, carbonate, and granite, reflecting the recycling of materials from the Siwalik Subgroups (Quick et al., 2020; Tamrakar et al., 2008).

Fig. 1: Geological Map of Study Area

Research Methodology

Field Sampling Based on Isopach Map

The field sampling was conducted at 15 strategically chosen sites across the study area, selected according to the thickness contours on the isopach map (Figure 2). These sites were chosen to ensure a representative sampling of gravel deposits in areas where thickness was anticipated to vary significantly:

- **Site Selection:** The isopach map indicated zones with varying gravel bed thicknesses, allowing for the identification of high, medium, and low-thickness areas for sampling.
- **Sampling Procedure:** At each site, the thickness of the gravel bed was measured. A GPS device was used to record the precise location of each sample, ensuring accurate spatial correlation with the isopach map.
- **Sample Collection:** Gravel samples were collected from the surface to the base of the gravel bed to reflect the full vertical profile of the deposit at each site.

Fig. 2: Isopach Map of Gravel Resource throughout the study area.

Laboratory analysis

1. Physical Properties

Specific Gravity, Density and Water Absorption

The laboratory procedures for specific gravity and water absorption were followed according to ASTM C127 (2011). The test sample was oven dried at constant mass at a temperature of $110 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$. The oven dry (OD) mass of sample was recorded. Subsequently, the sample was immersed in water at room temperature for 24 hr. Then it was removed and was soaked by moist cloth until all visible films of water were removed. At this stage the saturated surface dry (SSD) mass of the sample was recorded. The SSD sample was then immersed in water removing all entrapped air by shaking the container when immersed. The apparent mass of the sample was measured in water. The following equations were used to compute, specific gravity of oven dried sample (G_{OD}), Density of oven dried sample (D_{OD}) and water absorption (WA).

$$G_{OD} = \frac{A}{(B - C)} \quad (1)$$

$$D_{OD} = 997.5 \frac{A}{(B - C)} \quad (2)$$

$$WA = \frac{(B - A)}{(A)} \cdot 100 \quad (3)$$

Where, A is the mass of oven-dried test sample in air (in gram), B is the mass of saturated- surface-dry test sample in air (gram), and C is the apparent mass of saturated test sample in water (gram).

2. Mechanical Properties

Point Load Strength Index Test

Point load strength Index (PLSI) test is intended as an index test for the strength classification of rock material (Broch and Franklin, 1972). Irregular lumps with its width and thickness measured and tabulated, were used in this test following the procedure of ASTM D5731-02 (2002). Irregular lumps were loaded normal to the stratification, and the breakage load was recorded in KN. The PLSI that is denoted by symbol I_s was calculated using the following equation:

$$I_s = \frac{P}{(De^2)} \quad (4)$$

Where, P is a failure load (KN), and De is equivalent core diameter (m).

The equivalent core diameter is found out using the following expression:

$$De^2 = \frac{4A}{\pi} \quad (5)$$

Where, A is a minimum cross-sectional area of plane through the platen contacts points. The A was obtained from the products of average width and average thickness of the lump measured at least at two lines. The standard point load strength index, $I_{s(50)}$ was obtained by the product of size correction factor and point load strength index, I_s , using the following expression:

$$I_{s(50)} = \left(\frac{D_e}{50}\right)^{0.45} I_s \quad (6)$$

For the purpose of classification of strength of intact rocks, uniaxial compressive strength (UCS) was calculated applying the following relation:

$$UCS = 24I_{s(50)} \quad (7)$$

Aggregate Impact Test

The aggregate test sample of size between 12.5 mm and 9.5 mm and weight of about 500 g was prepared according to BS 812-112 (1990), and was filled in a cylindrical holder, one-third at a time and tamped 25 times with a tamping rod. The test -sample was then fixed in position at the base of the impact machine. The test-sample was subjected to a total of 15 blows by the 14 Kg weight of hammer, each being delivered at an interval of not less than one second. The crushed aggregate was then removed and sieved on the 2.36 mm sieve. AIV was then calculated using the following expression.

$$AIV = \frac{M_1 - M_2}{M_1} \cdot 100 \quad (8)$$

Where, M_1 is the initial weight of aggregate sample, and M_2 is the weight of aggregate retained on 2.36-mm sieve.

Aggregate Crushing Test

The aggregate crushing value (ACV) provides a relative measure of resistance to crushing under gradually applied compressive load. It was determined after BS 812-110 (1990). About 3 kg of sample of aggregate between 12.5 mm and 9.5 mm were put in cylindrical holder at three stages slightly tamping 25 times at each stage. The cylinder with the test sample and plunger in position was placed on a compression testing machine. The load was applied in such a way to achieve 400 kN load at 15 minutes. The crushed aggregate including the crushed portion was removed from the cylinder and was sieved on a 2.36- mm sieve. The ACV was calculated by using the following expression :

$$ACV = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_1} \cdot 100 \quad (9)$$

Where, $W_1 = 3$ kg is the initial weight of the dry sample, W_2 is the weight of the aggregate retained on 2.36 mm sieve.

3. Durability Test

Slake Durability Test

Durability of rocks against cyclic wetting in water and drying is measured by the Slake Durability Index (SDI). ASTM D4644-87 (2008) was followed to carry out SDI test to report standard SDI at second cycles, Id_2 . Furthermore, three more

cycles were added to see deterioration behavior of samples. Therefore, in total of five cycle test was adopted. Initially, the sample fragments were weighted and dried in the oven for 16 hours and allowed to cool at room temperature for 20 minutes, and weighed again. Thus the natural water content was calculated using the following expression:

$$W = \frac{A-B}{B} \cdot 100(10)$$

where, W is the percentage of water content, A is the mass of sample at natural moisture content (g), and B is the mass of oven-dried sample before the first cycle (g).

The lump test sample inserted in the drum was rotated at 20 rpm for a period of 10 minutes. Afterwards, the test samples were removed from the drum to dry in the oven for 16 hours at 105°C. After cooling, the sample was weighed to obtain the oven-dried mass for the second cycle. Again the cycle was repeated to measure the weight of the sample to obtain a final mass. The tested samples were retained to evaluate disintegration. The I_{d2} was computed as follows:

$$I_{d2} = \frac{W_2}{B} \cdot 100(11)$$

Where, I_{d2} = slake durability index (second cycle), B = mass of oven-dried sample before the first cycle in gram, and W_2 = mass of oven-dried sample retained after the second cycle, in gram. For assessing disintegration behavior, sample at two stages were tallied with Type 1, Type 2 and Type 3 patterns (ASTM D4644-87 2008).

Sulphate Soundness Test

The sulphate soundness test was carried out on the aggregate samples to determine the durability of aggregate against physical weathering. The test was done as per the standard procedure of determining the sulphate soundness of aggregates as ASTM C88–05 (ASTM International, 2005). The test sample of two kg of the size 50 mm down to 37.5 mm was prepared, and was washed with distilled water and then oven dried at 105–110°C. A saturated solution of magnesium sulphate having density 1.292 ± 0.008 g/mL was subjected to 48 hour immersion and drying cycles in which they were Immersed in saturated solution for 16–18 hour after drained for two hours then oven dried at 105°C for 24 hour and cooled for five hours at lab temperature. The sulphate soundness value (SSV) expressed in percentage was calculated as,

$$SSV = \frac{(W_1 - W_2)}{W_1} \cdot 100(12)$$

where, W_1 is an initial weight of sample (kg) and W_2 is the weight of the sample after five cycles.

Los Angeles Abrasion Test

Los Angeles Abrasion (LAA) test measures resistance of aggregates to abrasion and impact and is an indirect test of hardness of rock. The test was carried out in LAA machine in accordance with ASTM C535 (2009). To conduct the LAA test, the Grade A test sample that constituted of 5 kg mass of aggregate of 50 mm down to 37.5 mm size and 37.5 mm down to 25 mm size was prepared, and was placed in the LAA machine along with 12 steel balls. The machine was set to revolve for 1000 revolutions. After completion of revolutions, the steel ball was taken out, and the sample was placed in a tray, and was sieved at 1.7 mm sieve. The retained sample was weighed. The LAA Value was calculated using the following expression:

The following formula was used to calculate the abrasion loss in percentage.

$$LAAV = \frac{(W_1 - W_2)}{W_1} \cdot 100(13)$$

Where, W_1 is an initial weight of the sample and W_2 is the weight of the sample retained on 1.7 mm sieve.

Results

The Siwalik Group, located between the Main Boundary Thrust (MBT) and Main Frontal Thrust (MFT), separates the Lesser Himalaya from the Indo-Gangetic Plain (Ganser, 1964). It is divided into Lower, Middle, and Upper units based on lithology: Lower Siwalik with siltstones and shales, Middle Siwalik with sandstones and siltstones, and Upper Siwalik with conglomerates (Auden, 1935; Gansser, 1964; Hagen, 1969). Further refinement by DMG (1987) subdivided the Middle Siwalik. Photogeological surveys by Itihara et al. (1972) confirmed this division. The Siwalik Group was formed as a foreland basin deposit due to Himalayan uplift and erosion during the Miocene to Pleistocene epochs, with sediments transported by rivers and alluvial fans (DeCelles et al., 1998). The alluvial fan deposit of post Siwalik was formed in the hinterland basin due to active upliftment of the Himalayan Frontal Thrust and the upliftment of the southern belt Siwalik (Kimura, 1995; Tamrakar & Karki, 2019). The deposit comprises of quartzite dominant gravels recycled from the loosely consolidated conglomerate of the Upper Siwalik.

Fig. 3: Map showing graphic logs sample locations.

The lithological descriptions of gravel clast sizes show a clear spatial variation when analyzing from the southernmost to northernmost points and from west to east across (Figures 4, 5, 6, and 7) different sites (Khahar Khahare (ephemeral stream), Agarate Khahare, Gauritar Khahare, and Chisapani Khahare). In the southern sections, such as at K1 and K2, the deposits are largely cobbles and pebble gravels (Figure 4), with a predominant clast-to-matrix ratio of approximately 70/30. These sections indicate thicker cobble-pebble gravel beds, often reaching thicknesses of 5 to 6 meters, with sandy matrix support. Moving towards K9 and K10, the size of clasts remains consistent with cobble and pebble gravels, but the sandy matrix proportion slightly increases, showing a volumetric proportion of clast-to-matrix closer to 55/45 in some layers (Figure 4).

Fig. 4: Stratigraphic profiles showing various sedimentary structures of gravel, pebbles, and cobbles (G-Gravel, p-Pebble, cp-Coarse Pebble, s-Sand, P-Pebble, Co-Cobble, B-Boulder) of the Khahar Khahare

Fig. 5 : Stratigraphic profiles showing various sedimentary structures of gravel, pebbles, and cobbles (G-Gravel, p-Pebble, cp-Coarse Pebble, s-Sand, P-Pebble, Co-Cobble, B-Boulder) of the Agarathe Khahare

Fig. 6: Stratigraphic profiles showing various sedimentary structures of gravel, pebbles, and cobbles (G-Gravel, p-Pebble, cp-Coarse Pebble, s-Sand, P-Pebble, Co-Cobble, B-Boulder) of the Gauritar Khahare

Fig. 7: Stratigraphic profiles showing various sedimentary structures of gravel, pebbles, and cobbles (G-Gravel, p-Pebble, cp-Coarse Pebble, s-Sand, P-Pebble, Co-Cobble, B-Boulder) of the Chisapani Khahare

As we transition towards the north and east, such as in the Chi and Aga sections (Figure 5, 7), the gravel clasts exhibit similar characteristics but with more pronounced fine sand intercalations. For example, C1 and C2 (Figure 7) show massive horizontal beds with thick cobble and pebble gravel deposits (up to 5.5 m) with larger clasts, typically poorly sorted and sub-rounded to round. This indicates a more massive gravel deposit in the northern regions.

From west to east, the overall variation remains subtle. The Chisapani Khahare sections often show well-developed horizontal bedding with slightly smaller gravel layers and increased matrix content compared to western sections like Khahar Khahare or Agarathe Khahare. For example, sites such as C6 and C7 show increased fine sand layers intercalated with thinner gravel beds, particularly towards downstream sections, where clast proportions range between 55/45 and 40/60. This variability indicates that the gravel clast size decreases slightly from north to south and from west to east, accompanied by a corresponding increase in finer sand and matrix material, highlighting depositional processes influenced by proximity to source areas and sediment transport dynamics in these regions.

Description and Engineering Characteristics of Ballasts

Aggregates collected from different sampling locations are primarily natural and uncrushed, deposited by the Khahares (ephemeral streams) flowing from the high hills of the Siwalik zone to the confluence of the Karra Khola (Table 1). These samples, mainly composed of monomict quartzite, consist predominantly of quartz. They are recycled Precambrian

quartzites deposited during the Quaternary period, spanning from the Middle Pleistocene to the present age. The samples are observed to be free from fractures and disintegration.

Table 1: Description of study area location

S.N.		Locations	Elevation	Co-ordinates	Location	Description of samples
1.	K1	Khahar Khahare	697 m	27°21'25.23"N 85° 1'14.43"E	About 280 m away from ratomate police post towards south, upstream of the Khahar Khahare	Cobble, pebble and sand deposit with cobble 5%, pebble 35% and sand 60%
2.	K2		650 m	27°21'53.73"N 85° 1'31.86"E	About 180 m away from ratomate police post towards south upstream of the Khahar Khahare	Cobble, pebble and sand deposit with cobble 10%, pebble 40% and sand 50%
3.	K3		611 m	27°22'15.93"N 85° 1'59.30"E	Downstream of the Khahar Khahare about 150 m west of Riddhi siddhi cement plant on left bank	Consist of sand stone and siltstone at bottom, gravel with medium to coarse sand matrix
4.	K4		562 m	27°22'48.14"N 85° 2'5.80"E	About 210 m away from police post on downstream of the Khahar Khahare on right bank	Layer of medium to coarse sand with layer of gravels. Mostly consist of sand and pebble.
5.	K5		510 m	27°23'30.60"N 85° 2'5.65"E	About 210 m downstream of the Khahar Khahare from fire line road on right bank	Fine-medium-coarse reddish to yellowish sand layer with gravel
6.	K6		454 m	27°24'17.41"N 85° 1'59.32"E	Downstream of the Khahar Khahare about 310 m away from hetau-phaparbari road at kamane on left bank	Grey to white fine sand and pebbly sand with overall cobble 5%, pebble 30% and sand 65%
7.	K7		554 m	27°22'42.56"N 85° 2'11.09"E	About 350 m from Borle Kamane road towards downstream of the Khahar Khahare	Horizontal bedded sandy matrix supported cobble; pebbles gravel with few sand layers
8.	K8		512 m	27°23'2.97"N 85° 2'37.62"E	On downstream of the Khahar Khahare about 450m away from upasana church at fireline road towards east	Poorly sorted, sub angular to sub rounded gravel with matrix supported
9.	A1	Agrathe Khahare	555 m	27°22'34.61"N 85° 2'29.17"E	At downstream of the Agrathe Khahare on left bank at about 350m away from Borle – Chisapani road	Rounded to sub rounded, moderately sorted, sandy matrix supported gravel, grey to brownish fine to coarse sand

10.	A2		478 m	27°23'20.71"N 85° 3'36.22"E	About 170 m south west of Fapbari-hetauda road section at sundarbasti near river bifurcated section	Poorly sorted, sub rounded to rounded gravel, fine grey yellowish clayey sand
11.	A3		498 m	27°22'54.27"N 85° 3'37.32"E	About 950 m away from bifurcation towards south	Poorly sorted, sub rounded to rounded gravel with pale yellow fine sand
12.	A4		521 m	27°22'36.92"N 85° 2'54.87"E	About 1.1 km from jatte road towards upstream of the Agrathe Khahare at right bank	Poorly sorted, cobble, pebble with sand matrix, rounded to sub-rounded pebble dominated sand matrix supported horizontal layer
13.	G1	Gauritar Khahare	550 m	27°22'10.90"N 85° 3'1.76"E	About 400 m away from Bhore-Chisapaani road at Jatte on downstream of the Gauritar Khahare	Very poorly sorted, sub-rounded-rounded, cobble-pebble with sandy matrix
14.	G2		484 m	27°23'0.72"N 85° 4'11.08"E	About 280 m away from Ratomate police post towards south, upstream of Khahar khola	Sub rounded to rounded, poorly sorted, pebble dominated
15.	C1	Chisapani Khahare	600 m	27°21'59.70"N 85° 3'32.43"E	About 180 m away from Ratmate police post towards south upstream of the Khahar Khahare	Sandy matrix supported pebble, cobble with some sand flashes of sand; sub rounded and poorly sorted, clast – matrix 70/30.

Petrography Description

Table 2: Result of Petrography

Stratigraphic	Sample	*Quartz grain habit and fabric	Grain size (μ)				*Microstructure	**Non mica/mica Band Ratio
			Min	Max	Avg	mode		
Alluvial Fan Gravel	K1	inequigranular, sub-equant and elongate, intelocked, sutured	87	1200	338	200	Continuous foliation; Mica: 0.040 mm; Non mica: 0.400 mm	10
	K2	inequigranular, sub-equant and elongate, intelocked, sutured	55	350	220	200	Massive, interlocked, sutured, BGR>SGR; grains 85% (0.3 mm), subgrains 15%	

	inequigranular, subequant and elongate,					Continuous foliation; Mica: 0.010 mm; Non mica: 0.80 mm	
K3	sutured	35	300	60	80		8
	inequigranular, subequant and elongate,					Massive, interlocked, BGR>SGR; Grains 85% (0.8 mm), subgrains 15%	
K4	sutured	75	900	259	400		
	subequigranular, subequant and elongate, interlocked, sutured					Continuous foliation; Mica: 0.010 mm; Non mica: 0.080 mm	
K5		20	300	100	150		8
	inequigranular, subequant and elongate,					Massive, interlocked, sutured, SGR with few BGR; grains 80% (0.8 mm), subgrains 20%	
K6	sutured	17	1900	400	450		
	subequigranular, subequant and elongate, interlocked, sutured					Continuous foliation; Mica: 0.005 mm; Non mica: 0.200 mm	
K7		20	300	160	200		40
	subequigranular, subequant and elongate, recrystallized					Mica: 0.005 mm; Non mica: 0.200 mm	
K8		20	400	210	180		40
	inequigranular, subequant and elongate					Massive, interlocked, wavy foliation, BGR >SGR; grain 85% (0.4 mm), subgrain 15%	
A1	subequigranular, subequant and elongate, amoeboid	47	2000	208	400		
A2		173	800	384	600	Massive, interlocked, Grains with wavy foliation, grains 85% (0.5 mm), subgrains 15%	
	subequigranular, sutured, well siliceous					Massive, interlocked, orthoquartzite; grains 90% (0.5 mm), subgrains 10%	
A3	cemented	45	1200	456	610		
	subequigranular, elongate, irregular boundaries					Continuous foliation; Mica: 0.010 mm; Non mica: 0.100 mm	
A4		60	400	144	215		10
	subequigranular, mostly elongate, straight to irregular boundaries					Continuous foliation; Mica: 0.010 mm; Non mica: 0.100 mm	
G1		90	495	265	380		10
	inequigranular, subequant and elongate,					Massive, interlocked, sutured, BGR >SGR; grains 80% (0.3 mm); subgrains 20%	
G2	sutured	60	830	315	330		
	inequigranular, subequant and elongate,					Massive, interlocked, sutured, BGR>SGR; grains 85% (0.2 mm); subgrains 15%	
C1	interlocked, sutured	50	800	212	275		

*Microstructure: BLG=bulging grain recrystallization; SGR=sediment grain rotation

**Band Ratio = Mode of Non-mica thickness/Mode of mica thickness

The aggregates primarily consist of recycled Precambrian quartzites, exhibiting diverse grain sizes, habits, and microstructures. The quartz grains are predominantly inequigranular, subequant, and elongate, with interlocked and sutured textures, while some samples display sub-equigranular grains with amoeboid or irregular boundaries (Figure 7). Grain size varies significantly, ranging from 17 μm to 2000 μm, with average sizes between 60 μm and 456 μm and modes clustering around 200 μm to 450 μm (Table 2). Microstructurally, the samples demonstrate continuous foliation, with distinctions between mica and non-mica bands. The microstructural features, including bulging grain recrystallization (BGR) and subgrain rotation (SGR), reflect dynamic recrystallization processes. The non-mica/mica band ratio ranges from 8 to 40, with higher ratios indicating significant non-mica dominance in certain samples. Most samples are siliceous with minimal mica content, and orthoquartzite characteristics

Fig. 7: Microphotograph of sample A3, A4, K3, K8 under cross polarized light.

Physical properties

Table 3: Result of Specific gravity, density and water absorption of quartzite ballast

Sample Location	Mass of Oven-dry sample	Mass of saturated surface	Mass of saturated sample	RD or SG (SSD)	RD or SG (OD)	ARD or ASG = A/(A-C)	OD = 997.5 × {A/(B-	SSD = 997.5 × (B/B-C)	AD = 997.5 × (A/A-C)	WA = (B-A)/A × 100
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		in air (Kg) A	dry (SSD) wt. in air, (Kg) B	in Water (Kg) C	=B/(B- C)	A/(B- C)		C)) Kg/m ³			
Khahar Khahare	K-1	2.096	2.104	1.301	2.62	2.61	2.63	2602.07	2612	2628.23	0.38
	K-2	2.035	2.043	1.232	2.52	2.51	2.53	2501.43	2511.27	2526.34	0.39
	K-3	2.028	2.04	1.265	2.63	2.62	2.66	2608.55	2623.98	2649.55	0.59
	K-4	2.066	2.07	1.247	2.52	2.51	2.52	2504.05	2508.9	2516.28	0.19
	K-5	2.078	2.085	1.24	2.47	2.46	2.48	2453.02	2461.29	2473.51	0.34
	K-6	2.053	2.056	1.257	2.57	2.57	2.58	2563.04	2566.78	2572.7	0.15
	K-7	2.01	2.015	1.259	2.66	2.66	2.67	2650.33	2656.92	2667.96	0.25
	K-8	2.018	2.025	1.282	2.72	2.71	2.74	2707.4	2716.8	2733.14	0.35
Agrathe Khahare	A-1	2.039	2.048	1.261	2.6	2.59	2.62	2582.73	2594.13	2612.59	0.44
	A-2	2.091	2.1	1.269	2.53	2.52	2.54	2509.95	2520.76	2537.44	0.43
	A-3	2.075	2.087	1.299	2.65	2.63	2.67	2625	2640.18	2665.57	0.58
	A-4	2.042	2.049	1.272	2.64	2.63	2.65	2621.49	2630.47	2645.32	0.34
Gauritar Khahare	G-1	2.038	2.048	1.266	2.62	2.61	2.64	2599.62	2612.38	2633.3	0.49
	G-2	2.103	2.11	1.249	2.45	2.44	2.46	2434.99	2443.09	2454.94	0.33
Chisap- ani Kha- hare	C-1	2.043	2.053	1.244	2.54	2.53	2.56	2519.03	2531.36	2550.55	0.49

SG= Specific Gravity, OD= Oven Dry, SSD= Surface Saturated Density, RD= Relative Density, ARD= Apparent Relative Density, ASG= Apparent Specific Gravity K= Khahar Khahare, A= Agrathe Khahare, G= Gauritar Khahare, C = Chisapani Khahare.

The Specific Gravity (SG) values for the Khahar Khahare, SSD values range from 2.47 to 2.72 (avg. 2.58), OD values range from 2.46 to 2.71 (avg. 2.58), and ASG values range from 2.48 to 2.74 (avg. 2.59). In the Agrathe Khahare, SSD ranges from 2.53 to 2.65 (avg. 2.60), OD ranges from 2.52 to 2.63 (avg. 2.59), and ASG ranges from 2.54 to 2.67 (avg. 2.62). The Gauritar Khahare shows SSD values of 2.45–2.62 (avg. 2.53), OD values of 2.44–2.61 (avg. 2.52), and ASG values of 2.46–2.64. In the Chisapani Khahare, SSD, OD, and ASG values are 2.54, 2.53, and 2.56, respectively.

Density values also vary among the sections. The average oven-dry density is 2573.73 Kg/m³ (Khahar), 2584.79 Kg/m³ (Agrathe), 2517.31 Kg/m³ (Gauritar), and 2519.03 Kg/m³ (Chisapani). The saturated surface dry density averages are 2582.84 Kg/m³ (Khahar), 2596.38 Kg/m³ (Agrathe), 2523.18 Kg/m³ (Gauritar), and 2531.36 Kg/m³ (Chisapani). The apparent density averages are 2595.96 Kg/m³ (Khahar), 2615.23 Kg/m³ (Agrathe), 2544.12 Kg/m³ (Gauritar), and 2550.55 Kg/m³ (Chisapani) (Table 3).

Water absorption values range between 0.15% and 0.59% in the Khahar Khahare, 0.34% and 0.58% in the Agrathe Khahare, 0.33% and 0.49% in the Gauritar Khahare, and 0.49% in the Chisapani Khahare. The highest water absorption is observed in the Agrathe Khahare, while the lowest is in the Khahar Khahare (Table 3).

Mechanical Properties

Point Load Index Value

The Uniaxial Compressive Strength (UCS) of the collected samples was determined through point load testing on rectangular irregular lumps. The UCS values vary across the Khahare sections.

Table 4: Result of Aggregate Point load Test.

Lo- ca- tion	W 1 m m	W2 mm	W avg mm	T1 m m	T2 m m	T avg mm	Are a	De ²	Loa d (KN) ($\times 1000$)	Is (KN/ m ²) ($\times 1000$)	De	F=(De/50) ^{0.45}	Is (50) = F \times Is	UCS=Is (50) $\times 24$	UCS Classi- fication (ISMR 1981)
K1	52. 59	55.2 9	53.9 4	32. 71	36. 03	34.3 7	1853 .75	2361 .46	10.4 3	4.42	48. 59	0.99	4.36	104.65	very Strong
K2	48. 60	53.2 4	50.9 2	35. 27	34. 66	34.9 6	1780 .12	2267 .67	10.0 3	4.42	47. 62	0.98	4.33	103.85	very Strong
K3	51. 90	51.6 6	51.7 8	31. 98	32. 41	32.1 9	1666 .85	2123 .38	12.0 3	5.67	46. 08	0.96	5.46	131.07	very Strong
K4	60. 82	62.7 7	61.7 9	36. 53	40. 31	38.4 2	2373 .82	3023 .97	9.84	3.25	54. 99	1.04	3.40	81.51	Strong
K5	56. 06	58.1 3	57.1 0	33. 15	33. 24	33.2 0	1895 .27	2414 .36	10.0 0	4.14	49. 14	0.99	4.11	98.63	Strong
K6	54. 16	49.6 8	51.9 2	33. 46	34. 80	34.1 3	1772 .03	2257 .36	10.1 5	4.50	47. 51	0.98	4.39	105.46	very Strong
K7	42. 18	43.8 7	43.0 2	44. 62	46. 25	45.4 4	1954 .61	2489 .95	13.0 1	5.23	49. 90	1.00	5.22	125.29	very Strong
K8	53. 15	54.1 9	53.6 7	35. 28	38. 17	36.7 2	1970 .80	2510 .57	11.2 7	4.49	50. 11	1.00	4.49	107.84	very Strong
A1	49. 71	49.1 9	49.4 5	39. 11	37. 27	38.1 9	1888 .30	2405 .48	10.1 6	4.22	49. 05	0.99	4.19	100.49	very Strong
A2	55. 88	57.6 9	56.7 8	35. 9	34. 68	35.2 9	2003 .71	2552 .50	10.4 3	4.09	50. 52	1.00	4.11	98.53	Strong
A3	56. 63	58.0 3	57.3 3	33. 28	33. 95	33.6 1	1926 .92	2454 .68	10.3 1	4.20	49. 54	1.00	4.18	100.39	very Strong

A4	54.	56.7	55.6	45.	42.	43.6	2430	3095	10.0	3.25	55.	1.05	3.41	81.83	Strong
	57	4	5	12	22	7	.24	.85	6		64				
G1	49.	46.9	48.2	30.	28.	29.5	1424	1814	12.1	6.67	42.	0.93	6.20	148.89	very Strong
	47	5	1	51	60	5	.65	.84	0		60				
G2	61.	47.0	54.3	26.	27.	26.6	1444	1840	11.7	6.39	42.	0.93	5.96	143.04	very Strong
	59	4	2	13	06	0	.51	.14	5		90				
C1	57.	54.8	56.1	34.	33.	33.9	1902	2424	11.7	4.86	49.	0.99	4.83	115.82	very Strong
	34	7	0	11	73	2	.91	.09	8		24				

In the Khahar Khahare, UCS ranges from 81.51 MPa to 131.07 MPa, with an average of 107.28 MPa. In the Agrathe Khahare, UCS ranges from 81.83 Mpa to 100.49 MPa, with an average of 95.31 MPa. The UCS values for the Gauritar Khahare are 148.89 MPa and 143.04 MPa. The UCS value in the Chisapani Khahare is 115.82 MPa. The results are summarized in Table 4.

Table 5: Results of Aggregate Impact Test of the quartzite ballasts

Stratigraphic unit	Sample	Initial Weight (g)	Retained Weight from 2.36 sieve (g)	Passing Weight (g)	AIV (%)	Initial Weight (Kg)	Retained Weight from 2.36 sieve (Kg)	Passing Weight (Kg)	ACV (%)
Alluvial Fan Gravel	K1	512	399	113	22.13	3.073	2.382	0.691	22.49
	K2	542	440	101	18.63	3.017	2.410	0.607	20.12
	K3	527	417	110	20.82	3.074	2.474	0.600	19.52
	K4	513	393	121	23.53	3.066	2.444	0.622	20.29
	K5	544	438	105	19.30	3.093	2.532	0.561	18.14
	K6	520	419	101	19.44	3.062	2.404	0.658	21.49
	K7	527	409	117	22.28	3.085	2.440	0.645	20.91
	K8	518	400	118	22.78	3.08	2.287	0.793	25.75
	A1	505	399	106	20.95	3.041	2.405	0.636	20.91
	A2	516	394	121	23.37	3.707	2.385	1.322	35.66
	A3	516	398	117	22.67	3.088	2.457	0.631	20.43
	A4	540	424	116	21.46	3.102	2.351	0.751	24.21
	G1	520	417	103	19.83	3.0675	2.321	0.747	24.34
	G2	521	397	124	23.80	3.048	2.433	0.615	20.18
C1	560	437	123	21.96	3.063	2.351	0.712	23.25	

AIV percentages for uncrushed pebble quartzite ballast samples (Table 5) range 18.63- 23.53%. Specifically, sample K2 has the lowest AIV at 18.63% while sample K4 has the highest at 23.53%. On the other hand, the ACV percentages

samples range from 18.14 - 25.75%. Sample K5 exhibits the lowest ACV at 18.14%, whereas sample K8 shows the highest at 25.75%. Among the other samples, the ACV percentages fluctuate between 20.18% and 24.34%. It's noteworthy that sample A2 has a considerably high ACV of 35.66% indicating lower resistance to crushing. These results provide valuable insights into the quality and durability of the quartzite ballasts the lower AIV and ACV percentages generally indicating better aggregate quality.

Durability

The Slake Durability Index (SDI), which evaluates the durability and weathering patterns of the collected samples, was measured across five cycles. The 2nd cycle, considered the standard for comparison, shows varying values across the Khahare sections. In the Khahar Khahare, the SDI for the 2nd cycle ranges from 99.71 to 100%, with an average of 99.89%. The Agrathe Khahare has SDI values ranging from 99.86 to 99.93%, averaging 99.91%. In the Gauritar Khahare, the SDI values are 99.93% and 99.75%, while the Chisapani Khahare value of 99.66% (Table 6).

Table 6: Results of Slake Durability Index of quartzite ballasts.

Sample	Initial Oven-dry wt. (g)	Initial Oven-dry wt. before 1st cycle	Moisture Contents (%)	Oven dry wt. after 1st cycle (gm)	Oven dry wt. after 2nd cycle (gm)	Oven dry wt. after 3rd cycle (gm)	Oven dry wt. after 4th cycle (gm)	Oven dry wt. after 5th cycle (gm)	I1st %	I2nd%	I3rd%	I4th%	I5th (%)	Degradation type	Durability Classification
K1	645	645	0	645	644	644	644	644	100	99.84	99.84	99.84	99.84	I	Extremely High
K2	691	689	0.29	688	688	687	687	686	99.85	99.85	99.71	99.71	99.56	I	Extremely High
K3	615	614	0.16	614	614	614	613	613	100	100	100	99.84	99.84	I	Extremely High
K4	643	642	0.16	642	642	642	641	641	100	100	100	99.84	99.84	I	Extremely High
K5	637	635	0.31	635	635	635	634	633	100	100	100	99.84	99.69	I	Extremely High

K6	427	426	0.23	426	425	425	425	425	100	99.77	99.77	99.77	99.77	I	Ex-tremely High
K7	700	699	0.14	698	697	697	697	696	99.86	99.71	99.71	99.71	99.57	I	Ex-tremely High
K8	705	704	0.14	704	704	704	703	703	100	100	100	99.86	99.86	I	Ex-tremely High
A1	588	587	0.17	587	587	587	587	586	100	100	100	100	99.83	I	Ex-tremely High
A2	769	768	0.13	768	767	767	767	766	100	99.87	99.87	99.87	99.74	I	Ex-tremely High
A3	715	714	0.14	714	713	713	713	712	100	99.86	99.86	99.86	99.72	I	Ex-tremely High
A4	676	675.5	0.07	675	675	674	674	674	99.93	99.93	99.78	99.78	99.78	I	Ex-tremely High
G1	686	684.5	0.22	684	684	684	683	682	99.93	99.93	99.93	99.78	99.63	I	Ex-tremely High
G2	599	598.5	0.08	598	597	597	596	596	99.92	99.75	99.75	99.58	99.58	I	Ex-tremely High
C1	730	729.5	0.07	728	727	727	726	726	99.79	99.66	99.66	99.52	99.52	I	Ex-tremely High

Table: 7 Result Los Angeles Abrasion of quartzite ballasts.

S.N.	Locations	mass of sample passing from 25-37.5 mm sieve	mass of sample passing from 37.5-50 mm sieve	Total weight of sample testing (kg)	Wt. retained on 1.7 mm sieve after 1000 revolution	Loss in wt. (kg)	LAV (%)
1	K1	5.11	5.12	10.22	7.34	2.88	28.23
2	K2	5.07	5.11	10.19	7.64	2.54	24.97
3	K3	5.07	5.05	10.12	7.32	2.79	27.62

4	K4	5.05	5.25	10.30	7.09	3.20	31.10
5	K5	5.07	5.09	10.16	7.05	3.12	30.68
6	K6	5.07	5.14	10.20	7.10	3.10	30.43
7	K7	5.06	5.06	10.11	7.27	2.84	28.07
8	K8	5.09	5.09	10.18	6.80	3.37	33.16
9	A1	5.07	5.13	10.20	7.50	2.71	26.52
10	A2	5.06	5.05	10.11	7.24	2.87	28.43
11	A3	5.07	5.09	10.16	6.08	4.09	40.20
12	A4	5.02	5.10	10.12	7.16	2.97	29.31
13	G1	5.07	5.03	10.10	6.82	3.28	32.46
14	G2	5.08	5.15	10.23	6.60	3.63	35.50
15	C1	5.05	5.08	10.13	6.97	3.16	31.22

The Los Angeles Abrasion Value (LAAV), which measures the resistance of aggregates to wear, (Table 7). In the Khar Khahare, LAAV ranges from 24.97 to 33.16%, with an average of 29.37%. The Agrathe Khahare shows a wider range, from 26.52 to 40.20%, with an average of 31.11%. At the Gauritar Khahare, the values are 32.46 and 35.50%, averaging 33.98%. The Chisapani Khahare value of 31.22%.

Table: 8 Result of Sulphate Soundness aggregate of quartzite ballast

S. N	Locations	Initial Weight (Kg)	1st cycle wt. after immersion in MgSO4 and drying in oven (Kg)	2nd cycle wt. after immersion in MgSO4 and drying in oven (Kg)	3rd cycle wt. after immersion in MgSO4 and drying in oven (Kg)	4th cycle wt. after immersion in MgSO4 and drying in oven (Kg)	5th cycle wt. after immersion in MgSO4 and drying in oven (Kg)	Wt. after washing with BaCl2 Solution	SSV%
1	K1	2.098	2.099	2.101	2.099	2.1	2.1	2.098	0.02
2	K2	2.037	2.038	2.041	2.038	2.038	2.038	2.035	0.1
3	K3	2.031	2.031	2.034	2.033	2.035	2.032	2.03	0.07
4	K4	2.048	2.048	2.047	2.045	2.043	2.043	2.043	0.27
5	K5	2.085	2.087	2.087	2.086	2.088	2.083	2.081	0.22
6	K6	2.077	2.08	2.084	2.077	2.076	2.076	2.075	0.12
7	K7	2.01	2.014	2.016	2.014	2.015	2.011	2.008	0.12
8	K8	2.02	2.023	2.024	2.021	2.017	2.019	2.018	0.12
9	A1	2.039	2.043	2.047	2.04	2.044	2.038	2.036	0.2
10	A2	2.098	2.102	2.097	2.098	2.099	2.097	2.094	0.24

11	A3	2.079	2.079	2.085	2.079	2.077	2.077	2.075	0.19
12	A4	2.046	2.049	2.05	2.051	2.053	2.047	2.044	0.15
13	G1	2.043	2.045	2.045	2.047	2.047	2.041	2.04	0.17
14	G2	2.027	2.028	2.033	2.032	2.032	2.032	2.027	0.02
15	C1	2.048	2.05	2.052	2.049	2.05	2.047	2.044	0.2

The Sulfate Soundness Value (SSV), which evaluates the resistance of aggregates to chemical weathering, (Table 8). In the Khahar Khahare, the SSV ranges from 0.02 to 0.27%, with an average of 0.11%. The Agrathe Khahare shows values ranging from 0.15 to 0.24%, with an average of 0.19%. In the Gauritar Khahare, the MSSV ranges from 0.02 to 0.17%. At the Chisapani Khahare, the SSV is 0.20%.

Evaluation of the Quartzite Samples on Basis of Outcome

The rating table is prepared for the suitability assessment of the sample from different locations (Table 9). Here, samples are assigned different value on range as per their result percentage which is on the basis of various standard code and guidelines for using appropriate samples. The importance of rating sampling location according to result assist in quality control of materials, resource assessment, selection of quality materials, environmental consideration and regulatory of supply and demand. The ratings values are assigned from 1 to 3, with 3 indicating high suitability, 2 indicating medium suitability, and 1 indicating low suitability, as per the values obtained for different parameters. This table provides an overview of how each location rates in terms of its suitability for various criteria. Ratings are determined by comparing the test results against predefined thresholds, with higher ratings indicating better suitability.

This table provides a concise summary of the ratings for the Khahar Khahare, Agrathe Khahare the Gauritar Khahare and Chisapani Khahare sections across various parameters. It highlights the key differences between these fifteen locations in terms of specific gravity, water absorption, PLI value, ACV value, AIV value, LAAV value, MSSV value, and SDI value. The Khahar Khahare had most of rating medium. For the Agrathe Khahare it was good to medium. Also, for the Gauritar Khahare value ranges at medium grade. And that of the Chisapani Khahare had good rating. The up streams of the Khahar Khahare had medium rating and also same for down streams except spot eight. The up streams of the Agrathe Khahare had good rating whereas downstream had medium rating. For the Gauritar Khahare both upstream and downstream has medium rating.

Analysis this rating table, here high rating values are assigned by Agrathe Khahare where three spots out of four are assigned good categories this could be due to its strength and resistance to abrasion since it has all good rating on its physical characteristics as water absorption, specific gravity, density and density whereas other Khahares are also in medium categories since low rating in their physical properties that means they also can be used. All Khahares have high potential for use as aggregates in ballast, concrete pavement and construction materials.

Table: 9 Rating table with grade samples

Location		WA	ACV %^	AIV %	PLI %	SDI %	SSV %	LAAV %	Sp. gravity	Density Kg/m ³	*Total rating / value Points	Rating
K1	Value	0.38	22.49	22.13	4.36	99.84	0.02	28.23	2.62	2628.23		
	Rating	3	3	3	3	3	1	2	3	2	23	Good
K2	Value	0.39	20.12	18.63	4.33	99.85	0.1	24.97	2.52	2526.34		
	Rating	3	3	2	3	3	1	2	3	2	22	Good
K3	Value	0.59	19.52	20.82	5.46	100	0.07	27.62	2.63	2649.55		
	Rating	3	2	3	3	3	1	2	3	3	23	Good

K4	Value	0.19	20.29	23.53	3.4	100	0.27	31.1	2.52	2516.28		
	Rating	1	3	3	2	3	3	2	3	2	22	Good
K5	Value	0.34	18.14	19.3	4.11	100	0.22	30.68	2.47	2473.51		
	Rating	3	3	2	2	3	3	2	2	2	22	Good
K6	Value	0.15	21.49	19.44	4.39	99.77	0.12	30.43	2.57	2572.7		
	Rating	1	3	2	3	3	2	2	3	2	21	Me- dium
K7	Value	0.25	20.91	22.28	5.22	99.71	0.12	28.07	2.66	2667.96		
	Rating	2	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	3	24	Good
K8	Value	0.35	25.75	22.78	4.49	100	0.12	33.16	2.72	2733.14		
	Rating	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	3	25	Good
A1	Value	0.44	20.91	20.95	4.19	100	0.2	26.52	2.6	2612.59		
	Rating	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	3	25	Good
A2	Value	0.43	35.66	23.39	4.11	99.87	0.24	28.43	2.53	2537.44		
	Rating	3	3	3	2	3	3	2	3	2	24	Good
A3	Value	0.58	20.43	22.67	4.18	99.86	0.19	40.2	2.65	2665.57		
	Rating	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	3	26	Good
A4	Value	0.34	24.21	21.46	3.41	99.93	0.15	29.31	2.64	2645.32		
	Rating	3	3	3	2	3	2	2	3	3	24	Good
G1	Value	0.49	24.34	19.83	6.2	99.93	0.17	32.46	2.62	2633.3		
	Rating	3	3	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	24	Good
G2	Value	0.33	20.18	23.8	5.96	99.75	0.02	35.5	2.45	2454.94		
	Rating	3	3	3	3	3	1	2	2	2	22	Good
C1	Value	0.49	23.25	21.96	4.83	99.66	0.2	31.22	2.54	2550.55		
	Rating	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	2	24	Good

*Rating: 22-27= good quality; 15-22= Moderate quality; <15 Poor quality

Table: 10 Comparison of properties of ballasts with specification

Test		Procedure	AREMA (2010)	BS EN 13450 (BS 2013)	RDSO, (2016) Indian Railway	Gravel
Physical Properties	Density (Specific Gravity)	ASTM C 127	<2600 kg/m ³	-	-	2378.68 to 2786.77 kg/m ³ (2.37 to 2.81)
	Water Absorption (%WA)	ASTM C127	1 to 2%	-	1%	0.10% to 0.95%
Mechanical Properties	Point Load Strength Index (I _{s(50)})	ASTM D5731-02	Dry>1200 kg Wet> 800 kg		-	82 Mpa to 185 Mpa
	Aggregate Impact Value (AIV)	BS 812- 112	-	14-22 %	20%	18.63% to 23.80%

	Aggregate Crushing Value (ACV)	BS 812- 110	-	<22 %	-	18.14% to 35.66%
Durability	Slake Durability	ASTM D 4644-87	Not allocated	Not allocated	-	99.36% to 100%
	Los Angeles Abrasion Value (LAAV)	ASTM C535	35% max.	25%	30%	24.89% to 36.40%
	Sulfate Soundness Value	ASTM C88	< 5% (5-cycles)	1% Nacl-10 cycles	-	0.0% to 0.39%

Comparison of uncrushed quartzite with the specified ranges in railway standards are AREMA (2010), BS EN 13450 (BS 2013) and Indian Railway The density of the gravel samples meet the AREMA (2010) specification range of 2378.68 to 2786.77 kg/m³ compared to AREMA's requirement of less than 2600 kg/m³. However, the water absorption of the gravel is lower than both AREMA and Indian Railway's standards with a range of 0.10 to 0.95% compared to AREMA 1 to 2% and Indian Railway's 1% (Table 10). The mechanical properties of the gravel sample the point load strength index is meet the AREMA standards range of 82Mpa to 185Mpa. However, the gravel's AIV and ACV) fall within the BS EN 13450 and Indian Railway specifications with AIV range 18.63 to 23.80% and ACV range 18.14 to 35.66%.

Durability test of the gravel sample slake durability 99.36 to 100%. It does not allocate with specified standards. The LAAV is below the AREMA standard of 35% and also lowers than the BS EN 13450 and Indian Railway standards of 25% and 30%, respectively (Table 10). The magnesium sulfate soundness value is significantly lower than all specified standards with a range of 0.0 to 0.39% compared to AREMA's < 5% and BS EN 13450.

Discussion

The quartzite gravel samples from various khahare sections in Central Nepal Sub-Himalaya have demonstrated excellent mechanical and durability properties, making them highly suitable for demanding construction applications such as railway ballast and road construction. The Los Angeles Abrasion Value (LAAV), which measures resistance to wear, showed moderate values, ranging from 24.97 to 40.20%, indicating that the quartzite gravel has good resistance to abrasion, ensuring durability under traffic loads (Maharjan and Tamrakar, 2008; Pokharel and Tamrakar, 2022). The Sulfate Soundness Value (SSV), which evaluates resistance to freeze and thaw weathering, was low, ranging from 0.02 to 0.27%, reflecting the material's ability to withstand environmental degradation, particularly in areas with high moisture, chemical exposure and diurnal variation of temperature (Franklin and Chandra, 1972; Wu et al., 1998). These low SSV values make quartzite gravel suitable for environments prone to sulfate-induced deterioration, an essential feature for aggregates used in construction where chemical weathering is a concern (Okonta and Magagula, 2011).

The Slake Durability Index (SDI), which measures the material's ability to resist weathering and disintegration under wetting and drying cycles, was consistently high, with values ranging from 99.66 to 100%, indicating excellent durability and long-term performance, particularly in fluctuating moisture conditions and the results are comparable to quartzite railway ballasts studied by Sharma and Tamrakar (2023) and the gravel ballast studied by Pokharel and Tamrakar (2022). The Aggregate Crushing Value (ACV) values ranged from 18.14 to 25.75%, with lower values indicating higher resistance to crushing, which is vital for maintaining the structural integrity of construction materials under heavy loads (Indraratna et al., 1998). Furthermore, the Uniaxial Compressive Strength (UCS) values varied from 81.51 MPa to 148.89 MPa, demonstrating high to very high strength of the material under compressive forces (Selig and Sluz, 1978).

Water absorption values ranged from 0.15 to 0.59%, with lower values being preferable, as they indicate reduced moisture infiltration, thus maintaining the strength and durability of the material over time (Wnek et al., 2013). Specific gravity and density values also varied across the Khahare sections, with higher values indicating a denser and stronger material, ideal for construction applications requiring stability under load. The low water absorption and high specific gravity in the quartzite gravel contribute to its strength and resistance to weathering, making it a reliable choice for construction in regions with high moisture exposure (Gratchev, 2019; Daku, 2017).

The natural uncrushed gravel was evaluated for physical, mechanical, and durability properties, and the results were compared with specifications outlined by AREMA (2010), BS EN 13450 (2013), and RDSO (2016). The specific gravity values, ranging from 2.37 to 2.81, conform to AREMA's density requirement ($<2600 \text{ kg/m}^3$) and indicate sufficient material quality (ASTM C127). Water absorption values (0.10–0.95%) are well below the thresholds set by AREMA (1–2%) and RDSO (1%), highlighting the material's low susceptibility to weathering in wet conditions.

Mechanical properties, including the Point Load Strength Index (82–185 MPa), align with AREMA guidelines (Dry: $>1200 \text{ kg}$, Wet: $>800 \text{ kg}$), confirming the material's structural integrity under both dry and wet conditions (ASTM D5731–02). The Aggregate Impact Value (AIV) ranges from 18.63 to 23.80%, exceeding BS EN's range (14–22%) but within the RDSO limit of 20%, indicating moderate toughness against impact forces (BS 812-112). The Aggregate Crushing Value (ACV), varying between 18.14 and 35.66%, includes some outlier samples exceeding BS EN's limit ($<22\%$), reflecting reduced resistance to crushing forces in certain locations (BS 812-110). Similarly, the Los Angeles Abrasion Value (LAAV) (24.89–36.40%) complies with AREMA's maximum threshold (35%) but slightly exceeds the stricter BS EN limit (25%), indicating potential variability in wear resistance across samples (ASTM C535).

Durability tests showed excellent results, with Slake Durability Index (SDI) values between 99.36% and 100%, demonstrating high resistance to degradation during wet-dry cycles (ASTM D4644). The Sulfate Soundness Value (SSV) ranged from 0.0 to 0.39%, well within AREMA's guideline ($<5\%$ for five cycles), confirming strong resistance to chemical weathering (ASTM C88). These favorable durability results make the gravel suitable for ballast applications, especially in regions prone to environmental stressors. Overall, the test results indicate that gravel from Khahar, Agrathe, and Gauritar Khahare exhibits suitable characteristics for ballast, particularly in terms of low water absorption, high SDI, and low SSV.

Based on the rating system (Table 9), except the sample K6, almost all the samples performed excellently, with low water absorption, high SDI, and strong abrasion resistance, making them highly suitable for high-performance construction. These samples are ideal for infrastructure projects like railway ballast, where durabilities against abrasion and slaking are critical. In contrast, samples like G2 and K5, while still suitable for medium-grade applications, received lower ratings due to higher AIV and ACV values, indicating slightly weaker mechanical strength (Indraratna et al., 1998). The findings of this study align with previous research by Maharjan and Tamrakar (2008), Wnek et al. (2013), and Sharma and Tamrakar (2023), who have emphasized the suitability of quartzite for demanding construction applications due to its high strength, low water absorption, and durability under harsh environmental conditions.

In conclusion, quartzite gravel from the Khahare sections in Central Nepal proves to be an excellent construction material, offering superior durability, mechanical strength, and resistance to weathering and chemical attack. Its properties, such as low LAAV, ACV, and water absorption, combined with high SDI and SSV, make it particularly suitable for heavy-duty applications like railway ballast. The rating system used to evaluate the samples supports their suitability

for various applications, with higher-rated samples being ideal for high-performance infrastructure projects (Franklin and Chandra, 1972; Wu et al., 1998; Maharjan and Tamrakar, 2008; Wnek et al., 2013; Indraratna et al., 1998; Selig and Sluz, 1978; Sharma and Tamrakar, 2023).

Conclusion

- The quartzite gravels from Central Nepal, show excellent mechanical and durability properties. These gravels show low water absorption, high Slake Durability Index (SDI), and strong abrasion resistance and exceptional strength.
- The quartzite gravel for railway ballast showed strong durability with high SDI and low SSV meeting AREMA specifications. Water absorption values are well below the limits specified by AREMA and RDSO. However, mechanical properties showed variability. While LAHV mostly complies with AREMA's limit some values exceed the stricter IS standards. Similarly, ACV includes samples exceeding the IS limit, indicating variability in strength.
- Quartzite gravels from the alluvial fan deposits are the most reliable due to their high durability, low water absorption, and strong mechanical properties, therefore they can be used as an alternative to the crushed quartzite ballasts.

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